

THE METHOD OF LEARNING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *The study of foreign languages in modern society is becoming an inseparable component of the professional training of specialists of various profiles, and the successful solution of professional growth issues and the expansion of contacts with foreign partners largely depend on the quality of their language training.*

Key words: *professional training, issue, educational problems, teaching process, methodology.*

МЕТОД ИЗУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *Изучение иностранных языков в современном обществе становится неотъемлемым компонентом профессиональной подготовки специалистов различного профиля, и от качества их языковой подготовки во многом зависит успешное решение вопросов профессионального роста и расширение контактов с зарубежными партнерами.*

Ключевые слова: *профессиональная подготовка, выпуск, воспитательные проблемы, учебный процесс, методика.*

Nawadays, the school is designed to provide a certain level of foreign language proficiency, which could allow to continue its study during the period of university and postgraduate education, as well as independently. The success of training largely depends on the methodology of the teacher of a foreign language, on his ability to use various modern methods in the context of solving specific educational problems.

The content of teaching foreign languages is understood as a category that pedagogically interprets the goal of teaching foreign languages. Since the goal is a multidimensional education, the content cannot be single-component. Modern domestic researchers consider the content of education as constantly evolving category and single out in it both the subject (including spheres and situations of communication; themes, texts; communicative goals and intentions; regional knowledge, linguistic and regional knowledge; language material) aspect, and the procedural (contains skills and skills of foreign language oral and written communication).

The goals of teaching a foreign language are an important methodological category. The starting point in determining the strategic goal of education is the social order of society in relation to the younger generation. In particular, foreign language education for almost the entire twentieth century consisted of a quality possession of the subject. Then there was a turn from grammar-translation methods to the problem of practical mastery of a foreign language. However, the very concept of "practical knowledge of a foreign language" was clarified and was concretized depending on the level of development of the methodology and the goals of teaching the subject related to it, it was understood:

- mastery of speech within certain limits;
- the formation of skills and abilities to understand the thoughts of other people and express their thoughts (orally and in writing);
- development of speech skills in all types of speech activity;
- learning to communicate in a foreign language in the unity of all its functions:

cognitive, regulatory, value-oriented, etiquette.

Such dynamics of the development of the interpretation of the goal of teaching a foreign language reflects the essence of the development of methodology as a science and related areas of scientific knowledge.

The learning process is very voluminous and multifaceted. It is hard to imagine that all principles can be relevant for the whole process. Under the principles of learning, it is customary to consider the main provisions that determine the nature of the learning process, which are formed on the basis of the chosen direction and approaches corresponding to this direction. Clearly articulated learning principles will help you decide the question of how and what content of training to select, what materials and techniques to use.

Foreign methodologists note the importance of linguistic, psychological and didactic factors in teaching a foreign language, however, the concept of "principle of learning" is not a basic category of foreign methodology and is currently rarely found in publications, probably due to the fact that the term itself implies the dominant role of the teacher in the educational process, which is rejected by modern methodologists.

It should be noted that some authors recognize the need to take into account the principles of teaching and learning and highlight the following:

- cognitive principles: the principle of automation of speech units (automaticity); the principle of using intrinsic motivation (intrinsic motivation principle); the principle of using the student's personal contribution (strategic investment principle) - his time, effort, individual abilities, etc. - and a number of other principles;

- emotional-psychological principles (affective principles): the principle of "linguistic I" (language ego), which means that when mastering a foreign language, a "second self" is formed in a person, affecting his feelings, emotions, behavior, etc.; the principle of interconnected mastery of the language and culture of the country of the language being studied (language-culture connection). You should also consider qualities such as self-confidence, self-esteem, the ability to experiment and take risks when using new material in the process of speech imitation in a foreign language (risk-talking);

- linguistic principles: taking into account the influence native language to mastering a foreign language (native language effect); taking into account the peculiarities of mastering the language being studied as an intermediate language system (interlanguage is a constantly changing language system that is located between the native and studied languages and is inherently individual for each student; it improves as the language is mastered, approaching the system of the language being studied); the principle of communicative competence in the process of teaching a foreign language.

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